

TWO APPLICATIONS OF THE BELL POLYNOMIALS

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Cite This Article: R. Sivaraman, J. D. Bulnes & J. López-Bonilla, "Two Applications of the Bell Polynomials", Indo American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Review, Volume 8, Issue 2, July - December, Page Number 120-121, 2024.

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Abstract:

We show that the Hermite polynomials and the number of self-conjugate permutations of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ can be written in terms of Bell polynomials.

Key Words: Recurrence Relations, Complete Bell Polynomials, Self-Conjugate Permutations, Hermite Polynomials.

1. Introduction:

In [1, 2] we find an expression for the complete Bell polynomials:

$$B_m(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m) = \begin{vmatrix} \binom{m-1}{0} x_1 & \binom{m-1}{1} x_2 & \dots & \binom{m-1}{m-2} x_{m-1} & \binom{m-1}{m-1} x_m \\ -1 & \binom{m-2}{0} x_1 & \dots & \binom{m-2}{m-3} x_{m-2} & \binom{m-2}{m-2} x_{m-1} \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & \binom{m-3}{m-4} x_{m-3} & \binom{m-3}{m-3} x_{m-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \binom{1}{0} x_1 & \binom{1}{1} x_2 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -1 & \binom{0}{0} x_1 \end{vmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

Therefore:

$$B_0 = 1, B_1 = x_1, B_2 = x_1^2 + x_2, B_3 = x_1^3 + 3x_1 x_2 + x_3, B_4 = x_1^4 + 6x_1^2 x_2 + 4x_1 x_3 + 3x_2^2 + x_4, \quad (2)$$

$$B_5 = x_1^5 + 10x_1^3 x_2 + 10x_1^2 x_3 + 15x_1 x_2^2 + 5x_1 x_4 + 10x_2 x_3 + x_5, \dots$$

On the other hand, from [3] it is clear that the recurrence relation:

$$y_n = \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n-1}{j-1} x_j y_{n-j}, \quad n \geq 1, \quad (3)$$

Implies the following property in terms of Bell polynomials:

$$y_n = B_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \quad (4)$$

That is, (4) is the solution of (3).

The Hermite polynomials $H_n(x)$ [4-11] and U_n , the number of self-conjugate permutations of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ [12], verify recurrence relations with the structure (3), hence they can be written in the form (4), which is showed in Sec. 2.

2. Two Applications of (3) and (4):

The Hermite polynomials satisfy the recurrence relation [4-11]:

$$H_n(x) = 2x H_{n-1}(x) - 2(n-1) H_{n-2}(x), H_1(x) = 1, H_2(x) = 2x, \quad n \geq 2, \quad (5)$$

In harmony with (3) for $x_1 = 2x, x_2 = -2, x_k = 0, k \geq 3$, then from (4):

$$H_n(x) = B_n(2x, -2, 0, 0, \dots, 0), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

Thus:

$$H_0 = B_0 = 1, H_1 = B_1(2x) = 2x, H_2 = B_2(2x, -2) = 4x^2 - 2, H_3 = B_3(2x, -2, 0) = 8x^3 - 12x, \quad (7)$$

$$H_4 = B_4(2x, -2, 0, 0) = 16x^4 - 48x^2 + 12, \dots,$$

Verifying the differential equation:

$$H_n'' - 2x H_n' + 2n H_n = 0. \quad (8)$$

In [12] we find the following explicit formula for the number of self-conjugate permutations of $\{1, \dots, n\}$:

$$U_n = \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor} \frac{n!}{2^k k! (n-2k)!}, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (9)$$

Such that:

$$U_n = U_{n-1} + (n-1) U_{n-2}, \quad U_0 = 1, U_1 = 1, \quad n \geq 2, \quad (10)$$

Which it is compatible with (3) for $x_1 = 1, x_2 = 1, x_k = 0, k \geq 3$, then (4) gives the property:

$$U_n = B_n(1, 1, 0, 0, \dots, 0), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (11)$$

Thus $U_0 = U_1 = 1, U_2 = 2, U_3 = 4, U_4 = 10, U_5 = 26, \dots$

In [3, 13-15] there are more applications of the complete Bell polynomials.

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